

Invited Article

Facile purification protocol of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals for light-emitting diodes with improved performance

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ABSTRACT

Light-emitting diodes (LEDs) based on CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals (NCs) show excellent performance in terms of external quantum efficiency (EQE) and brightness. Removal of impurities after NC synthesis is a necessary and critical step to achieve such high performance. In fact, the optical and electronics properties of CsPbBr₃ NCs are greatly affected by how the NCs are purified from the synthetic by-products, unreacted reagents, and organic ligand excess. Perovskite NC purification protocols must consider the ionic nature of the inorganic core, the labile nature of the ligand to surface bond, and the dynamic equilibrium between the surface-interacting and free form organic ligands to prevent NC damaging with subsequent loss of photoluminescence. Nowadays, the most employed purification protocol involves NC precipitation based on a diminished non-polar environment achieved by adding a low-dielectric constant miscible solvent to the NC solution (i.e., ethyl acetate to toluene), followed by redispersion of the precipitate in a storage solvent. Here, we explored the possibility to precipitate impurities left in the NC solution exploiting variations in solubility at decreasing temperature: by taking NC solutions at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight and by collecting the respective supernatant we obtain CsPbBr₃ NC solutions which leads to LEDs with improved EQE. The freezing process at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ gives rise to NC solutions that retain the pristine optical and electronic properties while the LED performances display a 3 times increase in terms of EQE ($\text{EQE}_{\text{max}} = 8.9\%$) with respect to NCs treated with anti-solvent only. Finally, we show that our purification protocol can be applied to CsPbBr₃ NCs obtained via different synthetic methods, thus demonstrating the versatility of our facile purification protocol.

1. Introduction

Since their discovery in 2015 [1], colloidal metal halide perovskite nanocrystals (NCs) have been extensively researched as an exciting class of semiconductor materials for optoelectronics. Lead halide perovskites (CsPbX₃, where X is the halide X = Cl, Br, I) are characterized by remarkable properties such as tunable emission, narrow emission band (full-width-half-maximum, FWHM <100 meV) and near-unity photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) [2]. Perovskite NCs have been employed in various applications: photovoltaic devices [3–6], light-emitting diodes (LEDs) [7–10], photodetectors [11,12], and lasers [13,14]. In particular, green [15–17], blue [18,19], red [20,21] and white [22] emitting perovskite-NC based LEDs have seen a rapid improvement in performance thanks to surface engineering [23–25] and

device design [26–28] enabling an external quantum efficiency (EQE) up to 24% for green emitting devices [29]. Such result can mainly be ascribed to the high PLQY of perovskite NCs and the strong relation of the EQE with the former, as showed in eq. (1) [30]:

$$\text{EQE} = \gamma \eta_{\text{out}} \eta_{\text{PL}} \quad (1)$$

Here, γ is the charge injection efficiency, η_{PL} is the efficiency of the radiative recombination (i.e., PLQY of the emitters), and η_{out} is the optical outcoupling coefficient. LEDs based on NCs are built employing a multilayer structure formed by organic semiconductor polymers and the NC film as active layer. In such structure, charge carrier injection and transport are limited by the energy level offset at the interfaces of the various layers and the mismatch of the charge carrier mobilities. Charge carrier balance in the active layer can be achieved by a thorough

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investigation of the architecture of the device in terms of materials and thicknesses, and it can contribute to tune the efficiency of optical out-coupling as well. Therefore, to increase the EQE we can operate on the device architecture but also select an active material characterized by high PLQY. Here, the defect tolerant character of lead halide perovskites plays a fundamental role [31]. In fact, defect states in perovskite NCs do not have a strong influence on the non-radiative recombination, thus leading to high PLQY without the need of surface passivation or shelling as in the case of CdSe [2].

As synthesized CsPbX₃ NCs present various impurities in their respective solutions: by-products, unreacted reagents, organic ligand excesses, polymer impurities formed in the solvent [32]. Such impurities arise from the employed synthetic procedure and, as such they can vary from synthetic method to another; yet, all these different impurities can tamper with film formation, decrease conductivity and act as a PL quenching channel. In addition, the NC surface plays a crucial role in the final optoelectronic properties of NCs, with the dynamic ligand binding in CsPbX₃ NCs leading to fast ligands desorption (mainly as ion pair) and surface traps. Indeed, to fully exploit perovskite NCs in LEDs, an efficient purification protocol must be carried out after synthesis and the protocol must be capable of removing impurities without affecting the NC surface (i.e., damaging the NCs). To date, several CsPbX₃ NC purification approaches have been explored to achieve high NC solution purity, including precipitation and redispersion processes using specific nonpolar antisolvents [33], inorganic lead halide salts [28], ligands replacement [21], or novel techniques like gel permeation chromatography [34]. The key element in all the post synthetic purification processing is that CsPbX₃ NCs maintain their pristine optical and structural properties. Generally, the purification process by precipitation and redispersion of CsPbBr₃ NCs involves: (i) addition of a low-dielectric constant solvent miscible with the synthetic solvent to induce NCs precipitation, (ii) isolation of the NCs via centrifugation and removal of the supernatant containing the soluble impurities, (iii) redispersion of precipitated NCs in a nonpolar solvent for storage and film fabrication. Many cycles of precipitation and redispersion are needed to adequately purify the NCs from impurities and the anti-solvent employed may cause irreversible damage to the NC surface due to ligands displacement. To diminish this detrimental effect, ligand exchange reactions are widely employed to replace native ligands with others that exhibit stronger bonding to the NC surface. In our case, we employed a well-known ligand exchange procedure based on a quaternary alkyl ammonium salt (i.e. didodecyldimethylammonium bromide, DDAB) that effectively passivates the NC surface, thus enhancing the overall material stability [35]. We applied the ligand exchange protocol with DDAB to two different types of NCs: CsPbBr₃ NCs synthesized via hot-injection of Cs-oleate precursor [36,37], and CsPbBr₃ NCs prepared via benzoyl bromide hot injection approach [38,39]. As previously discussed, and despite the exchange to more strongly bonded ligands, in both synthetic approaches retention of structural integrity of NCs during purification and handling is difficult. For this reason, we developed a purification process suitable for both materials involving standard NC precipitation via addition of a low-dielectric constant solvent to the solution, followed by a novel freezing step at -20 °C overnight which induces precipitation of impurities in solution. Both NCs synthesized via the Cs-oleate route (NC-Cs), and the ones prepared via benzoyl bromide precursor (NC-Br) show similar performance in terms of PLQY (91 ± 9%), emission wavelength (512 nm for NC-Cs and 511 nm for NC-Br) after ligand exchange and purification. Importantly, the freezing step does not impact the light-emission properties of both types of NCs as demonstrated by the unmodified PLQY and PL spectra. Yet, LEDs based on NC purified via freezing process show improved performances with respect to anti-solvent only (EQE = 8.9% for the former and EQE = 2.5% for the NCs which were only purified via anti-solvent), thus indicating that the purification process plays a crucial role in improving perovskite NC LED performance.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals

Lead acetate trihydrate [(PbAc₂·3H₂O), 99.99%], lead bromide (PbBr₂, 99.99%), cesium carbonate (Cs₂CO₃, reagent Plus, 99%), benzoyl bromide (C₆H₅COBr, 97%), ethyl acetate (98.8%), methyl acetate (98.8%), toluene (anhydrous, 99.5%), 1-octadecene (ODE, technical grade, 90%), oleylamine (OLAm, technical grade 70%), didodecylamine (DiDDAm, 97%), oleic acid (OA, 90%) and didodecyldimethylammonium bromide (DDAB, 98%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Octadecene was dried at 120 °C for an hour and stored in a glovebox. All other chemicals were used without any further purification. Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene (PEDOT:PSS), poly-N-vinylcarbazole (PVK), poly[(9,9-dioctylfluorenyl-2,7-diyl)-co-(4,40-(N-(p-butylphenyl))-diphenylamine)] (TFB), 4-Butyl-N,N-diphenylaniline (Poly-TPD) and 2,2',2''-(1,3,5-Benzinetriyl)-tris(1-phenyl-1-H-benzimidazole) (TPBi) were purchased from Ossila.

2.2. Synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs - halide hot injection method

The synthesis is a modified method of the reported synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs that involve the benzoyl bromide hot injection [39]. 20 mL of ODE, 3 mL of OA, 156 mg of PbAc₂·3H₂O, 34 mg of Cs₂CO₃ (were loaded into a 100 mL 3-neck flask equipped with a reflux condenser, a thermocouple probe, and a magnetic stirrer. The solution was degassed under stirring at 115 °C under vacuum for 30 min. In the glovebox, 880 mg of DiDDAm were dissolved in 2 mL of toluene and the solution was then transferred into a 3 mL syringe. The secondary alkylamine solution was injected into the cations precursor solution under nitrogen flow. After adding the amine ligand, the reaction mixture was kept at 115 °C under stirring until complete metal salt dissolution. The solution was cooled and stabilize at 80 °C (injection temperature). Meanwhile, the halide precursor was prepared in the glovebox: 100 µL of benzoyl bromide into 1 mL of degassed ODE. The solution was swiftly injected into the flask and immediately a yellow solution was formed. The reaction was quenched after 19 s by immersion of the flask into a water-ice bath. The solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min while the precipitate was collected and centrifuged once again at 5000 rpm for 2 min. The obtained precipitate was then redispersed in toluene and the solution was finally treated via a ligand exchange reaction.

2.3. Synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs - Cs-Oleate hot injection method

2.5 mmol of Cs₂CO₃, 5 mL of OA, and 5 mL of ODE were loaded into a 25 mL flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer. The solution was degassed at 120 °C for 1 h, and then placed into nitrogen atmosphere and heated at 150 °C until a clear solution was obtained. The synthesis is a modified method of the reported synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs that involves Cs-oleate hot injection [36]. The synthesis was carried out as follows: 734 mg of PbBr₂ was weighed into a 100 mL 3-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer. 20 mL of ODE, 5 mL of OLAm, and 5 mL of OA were added to the lead salt. The solution was heated at 180 °C under stirring until the complete dissolution of PbBr₂, then 1 mL of Cs-oleate [0.5 M] previously prepared was swiftly injected into the solution. After 10s the reaction is quenched upon flask immersion in a ice-water bath. The solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min. The precipitate was collected and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 2 min to dry well the precipitate. Finally, the precipitate was redispersed in 20 mL of toluene and treated via a ligand exchange reaction.

2.4. Ligand exchange and purification

1 mL of DDAB solution (0.02 M) was added to 4 mL of NCs solution and it was stirred for 1 min. 7.5 mL of ethyl acetate was added to the solution and it was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 6 min. The supernatant

was removed, and the precipitate was well dried and redispersed into 5 mL of toluene. The solution was centrifuged at 1500 rpm \times 7 min and the supernatant was collected. The purification of the ligand exchanged NC solution was carried out as following: ethyl acetate was added to the NC solution in volume 0.5:1 and the solution was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 6 min. The precipitate was collected meanwhile the supernatant was treated by adding drop-by-drop ethyl acetate until a turbid solution was obtained again. The solution was then centrifuged at 6000 rpm \times 6 min the precipitate was collected in a new vial and redispersed in 3 mL of toluene. The process can be repeated at least 3 times without any impactful NCs modifications. For further purification, the solution was kept at -20 °C overnight [40]. The supernatant was then collected and used for device fabrication.

2.5. Optical characterization

The UV–visible absorption spectra were recorded using a Varian Cary 300 UV–vis absorption spectrophotometer. The PL spectra were measured on a Varian Cary Eclipse spectrophotometer using an excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) of 350 nm for all the samples. Samples were prepared by diluting NC solutions in toluene, in quartz cuvettes with a path length of 1 cm. The PLQY of NC samples in solution and film were measured using an Edinburgh FLS900 fluorescence spectrometer equipped with a xenon lamp and a monochromator. The PLQY was measured using a calibrated integrating sphere ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 390$ nm). All the NC dispersions were diluted to an optical density of 0.1 at the corresponding excitation wavelength to minimize reabsorption of the emitted light. The film was prepared via spin casting the same solution onto a clean glass substrate (15×10 mm²).

2.6. Transmission electron microscopy

Bright-field TEM images of the NC samples were acquired by a JEOL JEM-1400Plus transmission electron microscope equipped with thermionic source (LaB₆) operating at an acceleration voltage of 120 kV. The images were acquired by Gatan CCD camera Orius 830 (2048×2048 active pixels). Samples were prepared by drop-casting diluted solutions of NCs onto carbon film-coated 200 mesh copper grids for low-resolution TEM.

2.7. X-ray diffraction

The XRD analysis was performed on a PANalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer, equipped with a 1.8 kW CuK α ceramic X-ray detector operating at 45 kV and 40 mA. Samples for the measurements were prepared by drop-casting a concentrated solution of NCs on a zero-diffraction silicon substrate. All of the diffraction patterns reported here were collected at room temperature under ambient conditions using parallel beam geometry and symmetric reflection mode. Post-acquisition XRD data analysis was carried out using the HighScore 4.1 software from PANalytical.

2.8. Ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy

The UPS measurements were carried out with a Kratos Axis Ultra^{DL}D spectrometer, using a He I (21.22 eV) discharge lamp, on an area of 55 μ m in diameter, at a pass energy of 10 eV and with a dwell time of 100 ms. The work function (that is, the position of the Fermi level with respect to the vacuum level) was measured from the threshold energy for the emission of secondary electrons during He I excitation. A -9.0 V bias was applied to the sample to precisely determine the low-kinetic-energy cutoff, as discussed by M. G. Helander et al. [41]. Then, the position of the valence band maximum versus the vacuum level was estimated by measuring its distance from the Fermi level [42].

2.9. Device fabrication

Indium tin oxide (ITO) pre-patterned substrates were sequentially cleaned by sonication in deionized water and detergent (Hellmanex III), deionized water, acetone, isopropanol, and water (5 min each step). All substrates were then well dried via a N₂ flux. After oxygen plasma treatment the PEDOT: PSS (AI4083, Ossila) was spin-coated onto the ITO substrates at 4000 rpm for 40s and annealed at 140 °C for 20 min in air. Thereafter the substrate was transferred into a nitrogen-filled glovebox. The poly-TPD (8 mg/mL in chlorobenzene) or PVK (8 mg/mL in chlorobenzene) or TFB (10 mg/mL in 1–4 dioxane) were spin-coated onto PEDOT:PSS at 2000 rpm for 40 s. Poly-TPD was annealed at 110 °C for 20 min, while PVK at 120 °C for 20min, and TFB at 150 °C for 20 min. The NCs active layer was prepared via spin-coating of a toluene solution (15 mg/mL) at 2000 rpm for 40 s. Finally, TPBi (45 nm), LiF (1.5 nm), and Al electrodes (150 nm) were deposited on the top of the devices through thermal evaporation under high vacuum (4×10^{-6} mbar). The emitting area is defined by the overlap of the cathode with the ITO and is 4.5 mm². The concentration of the NCs dispersion was calculated from Lambert-Beer's law by using optical density at 335 nm and a published size-dependent extinction coefficient [43].

2.10. Device characterization

The current-voltage-luminance characteristics were measured using a Keithley 2636 source-measure unit coupled to a calibrate PDA 100 A Si switchable gain detector from Thorlabs. The output of the Si detector was converted into power (photon flux) using the responsivity of the detector. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) was calculated as the ratio of the photon flux and the driving current of the device. The electroluminescence (EL) spectra were collected using an Ocean Optics HR4000 spectrometer.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals characterization

As previously discussed, CsPbBr₃ NCs have been synthesized through two different hot injection approaches: hot-injection of Cs-Oleate (NC-Cs) [36] and a second method based on the hot-injection of benzoyl halide (NC-Br) [39]. NC-Cs is the most common approach based on hot injection of Cs-oleate in a reaction flask that contains both the divalent cation and halide precursors dissolved in 1-octadecene thanks to the presence of surfactants. In this case, the organic ligands that are involved in the nanocrystal growth are oleic acid and oleylamine, a primary alkylamine (Fig. 1a NC-Cs). In the second approach (NC-Br), the halide precursor is used as the last reagent injected into the reaction flask. In this case, the surfactants of choice are oleic acid and didodecylamine (DiDDA), a secondary alkylamine (Fig. 1a NC-Br). One needs to consider that primary alkyl amines possess a stronger interaction with the NC surface than dialkyl amines which show a decreased bonding energy with the surface [44]. The obtained NCs were then ligand exchanged with DDAB [35].

The two synthetic methods present differences in terms of injected precursors, surfactant mixtures and reaction temperatures. In particular, the two syntheses are characterized by a different proportion between oleic acid ligands and amines which passivate the NC surface; in fact, the benzoyl halide method (NC-Br) employing DiDDA leads to a NC surface passivated mostly by oleic acid [39]. On the other hand, the synthesis based on Cs-oleate (NC-Cs) gives rise to a NC surface passivated by both oleylamine and oleic acid [22]. Considering the stronger bond of the primary alkyl amine with the NC surface, these ligands can still be present on the surface after the ligand exchange procedure while oleic acid is completely replaced [44]. Fig. 1b and c show the optical absorption and PL spectra of NC-Br and NC-Cs solutions, respectively. Both NCs show excitonic features in their optical absorption spectra with

Fig. 1. Nanocrystals synthesis and characterization a) schematic representation of the NC-Br and NC-Cs, respectively, before and after ligand exchange reaction. Optical absorption (black lines) and PL spectra (blue and orange lines) of NC-Br (b) and NC-Cs (c) after ligand exchange treatment. d-e) Representative TEM images of NC-Br and NC-Cs respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

NC-Br displaying a well distinguishable peak at 488 nm (indicating a near-monodisperse size, Fig. 1S) and a narrow PL peak at 512 nm with a FWHM of 16 nm. On the other hand, NC-Cs show a PL peak at 513 nm with a FWHM of 18 nm, while excitonic features in the absorption spectrum are not clearly visible due to the increased polydispersity compared to NC-Br, (Fig. S1). The increased FWHM of the PL spectrum in NC-Cs compared to NC-Br is attributed to an increased size distribution (Fig. S1). The TEM images (Fig. 1d and e) show cubic CsPbBr₃ while the relative size dispersion analysis (Fig. S1) confirms the previous observations from the optical characterizations: NC-Br are 7.7 ± 0.8 nm in size and NC-Cs = 8.8 ± 3.8 nm. Both samples show a PLQY in diluted toluene solution of $91 \pm 9\%$. XRD patterns (Fig. 1S) indicate that both methods lead to nanocrystals that match with the orthorhombic structure of CsPbBr₃. The results are consistent with previous reports [29,39]. Furthermore, secondary phases such as Cs₄PbBr₆ (which are non-emissive) are not observed as indicated by the absence of the characteristic peak in the absorption spectra at 315 nm [45] and the XRD patterns.

3.2. CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals purification protocol

Both NC-Cs and NC-Br solutions have been purified from by-products and the excess of free ligands. Here, as free organic ligands we mean the non-coordinated ligands from the cations of the NC surface, such as OA and DDAB from Cs or Pb, respectively. Importantly, the organic ligands that do not interact with NC surfaces must be removed to ensure good film formation. Furthermore, free organic ligands act as electrical insulators due to their large energy bandgap, thus impacting charge transport in the NC film [46]. The purification flowchart is shown in Fig. 2; the method involves two steps of NCs precipitation via anti-solvent addition to the solution. The anti-solvent of choice is ethyl acetate (EtOAc) in ratio 1.5:1 with respect to the NC solution volume for the first cycle, and 1:2 for the second cycle (Fig. 2, leading to the solution highlighted with a red rectangle). The small volume of ethyl acetate used for the purification of the NCs does not impact their PLQY [36],

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the purification process. Red rectangle highlights the NC sample obtained by anti-solvent purification, while the blue rectangle displays the final frozen NC sample. The recycling process is carried out on the supernatant (green rectangle) of the anti-solvent treated NC solution. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

while the soluble impurities in the toluene/EtOAc mixture are discarded with the supernatant. Free metals-oleate represent the predominant impurities [43], together with polymerized solvent [32] (i.e. 1-octadecene), inorganic salts, native ligands in excess and the ones released

from the NC surface after the ligand exchange reaction [47]. To increase the yield of the purification step, the supernatant of the centrifuged solution has been recycled by adding drop-by-drop ethyl acetate until a turbid solution was obtained. The supernatant can be treated up to 4 times (Fig. S2) without any dramatic PLQY decrease (from $91 \pm 9\%$ to $84 \pm 8\%$ for NC-Br) of the final NC solution and enabling a highly concentrated solution for film fabrication. Following purification after anti-solvent precipitation, the samples have been further purified via a freezing procedure, similar to the one reported by A. Swarnkar et al. [40].

The freezing process at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ induces co-precipitation of large and colloiddally unstable NCs, toluene insoluble byproducts and organic molecules (Fig. 2, leading to the solution highlighted with a blue rectangle), thus removing further the non-bonded organic molecules from the solution by fractional freezing. Oleic acid and oleylamine and ODE have low melting point: $13\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $18\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ respectively; while DiDDAm and DDAB are solid in a wider temperature range and show high solubility in toluene. Generally, the solubility of a compound in a solvent decrease upon lowering temperature hence, the freezing process promotes the removal of the low melting point molecules and the ligands in excess by decreasing their solubility and precipitating them in solid form [48]. In addition, the freezing treatment have only a minor impact on the NCs (as proven by the slight decrease in PLQY to $84 \pm 8\%$ for NC-Br solutions and $87 \pm 9\%$ obtained after the NC recycling step, Table S1) since the displacement of ligands from the NC surface is less favorable at low temperature, thus preserving the grade of surface passivation. Furthermore, the NC solutions treated via freezing process show improved stability of PLQY under ambient storage (Table S1).

3.3. CsPbBr₃ light-emitting diodes optimization

Following NCs synthesis, characterization, and purification, we focused on the LED architecture optimization. In particular, we tested three different hole-transport layers (HTL) in our devices maintaining the same perovskite sample (NC-Br): poly[(9,9-dioctylfluorenyl-2,7-diyl)-co-(4,40-(N-(p-butylphenyl))-diphenylamine)] (TFB), poly-N-vinylcarbazole (PVK), and 4-Butyl-N,N-diphenylaniline (poly-TPD, see scheme in Fig. 3a). We focused on hole injection as this is typically less efficient than electron injection due to the higher energy barrier between the valence band (VB) of the perovskite NCs and the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of the HTLs [36]. Fig. 3b shows the band energy diagram of the materials in the LED structure; the values are obtained from literature for all materials while the valence band and the conduction band of the NCs were measured via ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS, Fig. S3). The HTL materials were selected based on their HOMO level energies that must be compatible with a low energy barrier for hole injection, and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) suitable for electron blocking [16,49,50]. The main device structure has been kept the same in order to compare the influence of the HTLs used. The structure is the following: ITO (~ 100

nm)/PEDOT:PSS (~ 40 nm)/HTLs/NC-Br (~ 35 nm)/TPBi (~ 45 nm)/LiF (~ 1.5 nm)/Al (~ 150 nm). We have maximized the performance of each HTL by monitoring the EQE of LEDs at varying HTL thickness (not shown), thus obtaining the following optimized thickness of ~ 25 nm for poly-TPD, ~ 15 nm for TFB and ~ 20 nm for PVK. Fig. 3c shows the EQE of devices with different HTLs: a maximum EQE of 2.5% is obtained for poly-TPD. Therefore, the structure that has been used to compare the efficiency of NC film obtained from frozen solutions and not-frozen ones presents poly-TPD as HTL. Fig. S4 shows the effect of different HTLs on the current density (J) - voltage (V) - luminance (L) characteristics of the LEDs.

As reported in Table 1, the luminance, and the turn-on voltage of devices with poly-TPD as HTL are improved compared to those based on TFB or PVK. The maximum luminance achieved is $2653\text{ cd}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for poly-TPD, this result is around 4 times the maximum luminance obtained with TFB and two orders of magnitude more than PVK. Devices based on TFB display higher current density (196 mA cm^{-2} at 7 V) compared to that of poly-TPD of 90 mA cm^{-2} , which is nearly double the maximum current density reached for PVK. The LEDs based on PVK are characterized by a low current density and high turn-on voltage (3.8 V) while poly-TPD and TFB show a similar turn-on voltage at 3.4 V. The PVK possesses a deep HOMO that is close to the NCs VB, but the carrier mobility is 2 orders of magnitude lower than poly-TPD and 4 orders less than TFB [51]. This means that even if the energy barrier between the HOMO of PVK and the VB of NCs is lower compared to the other two HTL materials, PVK is unable to supply enough holes to the active layer.

3.4. Impact of the purification protocol on LEDs performance

We have fabricated LEDs employing the optimized architecture previously discussed (ITO/PEDOT:PSS/poly-TPD/perovskite NCs (35 nm)/TPBi/LiF/Al, Fig. 4a, an SEM image of a NC film is reported in Fig. S5) and NCs obtained via the two synthetic methods (NC-Cs and NC-Br) before and after application of a freezing procedure during purification. Fig. 4b shows the energy band diagram of the obtained devices: the values for all materials are obtained from literature [24,25], while the values of the CsPbBr₃ NCs were measured via UPS (Fig. S3). The impact of the purification process is more evident in the LEDs (Fig. 4c) where the EQE for both NC-Cs (dashed curves) and NC-Br (solid

Fig. 3. Study of different hole transport materials (HTMs) and given performances. a) Device architecture scheme and the HTMs employed, such as TFB, PVK and poly-TPD, b) energy band diagram of the HTLs and the emissive material, CsPbBr₃ NCs, c) EQE of the best devices based on different HTLs: poly-TPD (green curve) leads to improved EQE compared to TFB (light blue curve) and PVK (blue curve). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Device structure scheme and characterization. a) Scheme of the device structure and energy band diagram, b) External quantum efficiency as a function of the current density of LED-Br (solid curves) and LED-Cs (dashed curves). The red curves show the EQE curves of LEDs based on NC-Br1 and NC-Cs.1, while the blue curves represent LEDs embedding NC-Br2 and NC-Cs.2. d, e) Electroluminescence spectra of NC-Br and NC-Cs respectively. The insets show pixels under applied bias. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

curves) dramatically improves following the freezing procedure during purification. In Fig. 4c, LED-Br.2 and LED-Cs.2 have been both fabricated with NCs purified with the additional freezing steps, while LED-Br.1 and LED-Cs.1 employ NCs that have purified via anti-solvent process only. The devices embedding NC-Br purified via freezing show EQE up to 8.9% while for anti-solvent treated only NCs (red curves) the max EQE is 2.5% (Fig. 4c). Similarly, all other relevant performance parameters show an improvement in LED-Br.2 (Fig. S6): the maximum luminance increased to $12129 \text{ cd} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ from $2653 \text{ cd} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$, the turn-on voltage decreases from 3.4 V to 3.1 V. The enhancement in performance, which arises from the freezing procedure, is also visible in the LEDs based on NC-Cs. The maximum efficiency obtained from LED-Cs.1 is 2.3% (dashed red curve in Fig. 4c) while after freezing the EQE increases up to 7.7% (dashed blue curve, Fig. 4c). The luminance increases from $5223 \text{ cd} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ for LED-Cs.1 to $12040 \text{ cd} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ for LED-Cs.2 while the turn on voltage decreases from 3.2 V to 3.0 V (Fig. S6). Current density is higher for LED-Cs.1 than LED-Cs.2 ($223 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ vs $198 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ at 7 V), while LED-Br.2 show decreased current density following the freezing step ($112 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ vs $178 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ at 7 V). Fig. 4d and e shows the EL spectra of LED-Br.2 and LED-Cs.2 respectively. The EL spectra have a narrow peak characterized with a FWHM of 22 nm for LED-Cs.2 and 23 nm for LED-Br.2. The EL maximum is at 513 nm for LED-Cs.2 and 512 nm for LED-Br.2; no substantial red-shift of the EL with respect to the PL is observed. Furthermore, the EL spectra are without any parasitic emission of neighboring organic layer. The improved performance is demonstrated by 3 times increase in EQE for LEDs based on NCs that underwent the freezing purification protocol. This can be tentatively ascribed to the increased purity of the NC solutions which do not contain impurities harmful for the LED performance and a general improvement in film formation following the freezing procedure (see Fig. S7). Importantly, the freezing procedure has a similar impact on NCs obtained via different synthetic approaches, indicating the versatility of this additional purification step.

4. Conclusions

In this work we have synthesized CsPbBr₃ NCs via two different

routes: hot injection of Cs-oleate [36] and hot-injection of benzoyl bromide [39]. Following a ligand exchange reaction with DDAB, both samples show similar optical and morphological properties. Following these findings, we have tested various HTLs for the fabrication of LEDs and we identified poly-TPD as the best material to improve device performance. An optimized purification protocol has been developed and applied to both samples. The purification process plays a central role in improving the performance of LEDs. The additional freezing step that we propose does not show a detrimental effect on the optical properties of NC solutions while it remarkably affects the properties of respective LEDs. Here, the EQE increases from 2.5% to 8.9% for LED-Br thanks to the freezing purification. The correlated performance also increases; the maximum luminance is enhanced by a factor 5 for LED-Br while LED-Cs see the luminance increases 3 times. Another key parameter is the turn on voltage which decreases from 3.4 V to 3.1 V for LED-Br and of 0.2 V for the LED-Cs. Finally, by comparing LEDs based on the two samples, nanocrystals synthesized via the benzoyl bromide route display EQE = 8.9%, which is higher than the EQE of LEDs based on NC obtained via the hot-injection of Cs-oleate (7.7%). Our findings are of importance to further improve the performance of LEDs based on CsPbBr₃ NCs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Manuela De Franco: Conceptualization, Investigation, Visualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Matilde Cirignano:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Tullio Cavattoni:** Investigation. **Houman Bahmani Jalali:** Investigation. **Mirko Prato:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Francesco Di Stasio:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Supporting information for

Facile Purification Protocol of CsPbBr₃ Nanocrystals for Light-emitting Diodes with improved performance

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Figure S1 Size dispersion distribution of a) NC-Br and b) NC-Cs. c) XRD patterns of NC-Br (blue), and NC-Cs (orange) with orthorhombic CsPbBr₃ reference (black bars, code: 96 451 0746).

Figure S2 Optical and morphological properties of NC-Br fractions obtained from recycling process. a) Absorption (dark curves) and PL (greenish curves) of the 1st (top panel) to the 4th (bottom panel) fractions, b) Transmittance electron microscopy TEM images (scale bar 100 nm) and corresponding (c) size distribution analysis of each fraction

Table S1 Time evolution of the Photoluminescence quantum yield of DDAB exchanged NCs after 1 week, 3 weeks and for frozen NC solutions.

PLQY	NC-Br	NC-Cs
DDAB	91 ± 9	91 ± 9
After 1 week	90 ± 7	89 ± 9
After 3 weeks	85 ± 9	77 ± 8
Frozen sol.	84 ± 8	87 ± 9
Frozen sol. after 3 weeks	82 ± 8	78 ± 8

Figure S3 Representative UPS spectrum of a CsPbBr₃ NC film spun-cast on a substrate. The photoemission onset is directly correlated with the work function of the material. The region close to the Fermi level (Binding Energy = 0) shows the position of the valence band maximum. A linear fitting (red lines) was employed to extract the work function and the valence band energy values.

Figure S4 Performance of devices based on different HTL. Current density (J)-Voltage (V)- Luminance (L) characteristics of devices embedding a) TFB; b) PVK; c) poly-TPD.

Figure S5 SEM micrograph of a CsPbBr₃ NC film spun-cast on a Si substrate. The obtained film shows complete substrate coverage.

Anti-solvent treated NC

Freezing purified NC

Figure S6 Characterization of LEDs embedding NCs purified by anti-solvent only (a-b) and via anti-solvent and freezing (c-d).
 b) JVL curves of LED-Br.1 and b) LED-Cs.1, c) JVL curves of LEDs-Br.2 and d) of LEDs-Cs.2.

Figure S7 SEM micrographs at different magnifications of CsPbBr₃ NC film spun-cast on a Si substrate before (a, b) and after (c, d) the freezing process. The freezing process leads to improved film formation through the removal of impurities which give rise to “dendritic-like” structures (a) as well as leading to improved film coverage (b and d).